

**GROWTH, SPECTROSCOPIC AND OPTICAL STUDIES OF A NEW SEMIORGANIC
NONLINEAR OPTICAL CRYSTAL: L-VALINE MAGNESIUM NITRATE**

S.Janarthanan, M.Selvapandiyan*

Department of Physics, Periyar University PG Extension Centre, Dharmapuri-636701

Email: jana.physics@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A new semiorganic nonlinear optical crystal, L-Valine Magnesium Nitrate (LVMN), has been synthesized and good optical quality single crystals were grown by slow evaporation technique. The grown crystal was characterized by using FT-IR, UV-vis-NIR and DSC-TGA. The presence of various functional groups was confirmed by FT-IR spectroscopic technique. The UV-vis-NIR spectrum indicates that the crystal has very good absorption in the entire visible and near IR region spectrum suggesting the suitability of the material for NLO applications. The thermal stability of crystal was determined by DSC-TGA studies and mechanical stabilities of crystal have been confirmed by Vicker's microhardness study. The second harmonic generation behavior of LVMN crystal was tested by Kurtz-Perry powder technique.

Keywords: L-Valine Magnesium Nitrate, infrared spectrum, optical transmission spectrum, thermal analysis, and SHG test